

THE BRAND POSITIONING OF JISHOU DRUM CULTURAL FESTIVAL BASED ON SPECTATOR'S EVALUATION CHARACTERISTICS, HUNAN, CHINA

JIANXIN LIU

Doctor of Philosophy Program Student, Sport Management, College of Innovation and Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand. Email: s64584950006@ssru.ac.th.

NUTTAVUT PHONSRI *

Sport Management, College of Innovation and Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand. *Corresponding Author Email: nuttavut.ph@ssru.ac.th.

BUNJOB PIROMKAM

Lecturer, Sport Management, College of Innovation and Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand. Email: bunjob.pi@ssru.ac.th.

BOONYADA PAHASING

Lecturer, College of Innovation in Sports Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Thailand. Email: boonyada.pa@ssru.ac.th.

Abstract

As the central city of the drum Culture Festival, Jishou has been actively organizing various sport events in recent years, in order to promote the development of the sport industry and enhance the brand image of the city. Taking Jishou residents as the survey object, taking Jishou Drum Culture Festival as the empirical research object, and combining qualitative and quantitative research methods, the influence of evaluation characteristics, brand identity and brand recognition on the brand positioning of Jishou Sport is studied. Data from 480 questionnaires were processed and analyzed using SPSS and AMOS software. This study has three research objectives: 1) To investigate the current situation of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival, Hunan, China. 2) To analyze the relationship between evaluation characteristics, brand identity, brand cognition and brand Positioning of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival, Hunan, China. 3) To evaluate the impact of evaluation characteristics, brand identity, brand cognition and brand Positioning of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival in the model, Hunan, China. The study found that the Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand identity. Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand cognition. Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand positioning. Brand identity has a significant positive impact on brand positioning. Brand cognition has a significant positive impact on brand positioning. Brand identity plays a mediating role in the influence of evaluating characteristics on brand positioning. Brand cognition plays a mediating role in the influence of evaluation characteristics on brand positioning. Finally, a model of the influence of evaluating characteristics, Brand cognition, Brand identity on the brand positioning China was constructed (Chi-square=3625.006, DF=2635, Chi/DF=1.234, GFI=0.831, RMSEA=0.015, NFI=0.825, and NNFI=0.943). Therefore, this study is helpful to understand the overall status quo, influencing factors and mode promotion and application of Jishou sport city brand, and to lay a certain theoretical foundation for the research related to the city brand of sport events.

Keywords: Brand Positioning, Jishou Drum Cultural Festival, Evaluation Characteristics.

1. INTRODUCTION

On September 17 of the 2019, the "Opinions of the General Office of the State Council on promoting the high quality development of national fitness and sport consumption to promote the high quality development of the sport industry proposed to build a group of well-known enterprises and independent brands, and mentioned that the development of the sport industry with the Yangtze River Delta and other areas, Create the growth pole of the sport industry.

The Jishou Drum Culture Festival has the characteristics and highlights of international, interaction, originality, and marketability. It is a grand event for international drum culture, Performance competition, participation in the whole people, inspiring carnival, and detonating the market. The theme "World Encouragement Instead of the World", the main body of the event is a "opening ceremony patrol international drum cultural exchange meeting" by the five continents of different skin colors drum teams.

According to the Jishou International Drum Culture Festival, the brand benefits are not outstanding, and there are problems such as not fully utilizing local advantages and not formulating marketing plans for the spectator. In order to improve the asset value of Jishou International Drum Culture Festival, this article selects the perspective of spectator evaluation characteristics and verifies the mechanism of spectator evaluation characteristics and brand positioning, thereby helping the organization of Jishou International Drum Culture Festival clarify the direction of its positioning strategy and occupy the position in the hearts of consumers. Fight for a place and extend to the practice of other domestic sport event brands. In order to make this path more feasible, this study also introduced brand identity and brand cognition as intermediary variables to explore their role in evaluating characteristics to brand positioning.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand positioning means that companies target target consumers and determine a unique brand image for their products based on their understanding and importance of the brand, so as to gain the love and support of target consumers, which shows that the influencing factors of brand positioning constitute a linear framework. The theoretical framework obtained through comprehensive research elements includes the following three variables: 1) positioning difference (Integrate), 2) positioning accuracy (Unified), 3) Positioning competitiveness (Evaluate). Zhou (2023)

Brand identity is linked to self-concept, and consumers will have an emotional impact on the brand. Attachment, and manifested through purchases, These studies distinguish between personal identity, social identity and organizational identity, and study brand identity from different dimensions, providing ideas and methods for brand development. Zhao (2019)

Brand cognition is consumers' impression and feelings of the brand, and the understanding and evaluation of the brand's value and characteristics, this study divided the brand cognition into four dimensions, including brand identification, brand reputation, brand association, and brand loyalty. Dong (2023)

evaluating characteristics is the comparison between the customer perception and expectation of product quality, which is intuition and expectation, A function of the difference between the two, there are three main points of view on the determinants of sport spectator's evaluation characteristics, namely: Emotion (Quality-aware, A sense of trust and satisfaction), Attitude (Cognitive evaluation, emotional experience, behavioral intention), Behavior (Purchase intention, time). Kotler (2022)

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- H1: Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand identity.
- H2: Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand cognition.
- H3: Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand positioning.
- H4: Brand identity has a significant positive impact on brand positioning.
- H5: Brand cognition has a significant positive impact on brand positioning.
- H6: Brand identity plays a mediating role in the influence of evaluating characteristics on brand positioning.
- H7: Brand cognition plays a mediating role in the influence of evaluation characteristics on brand positioning.

Figure 1: Variable structure diagram

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to the sum of the measurement dimensions of each variable (12 items), and 240 live spectator are randomly selected for investigation. Considering the need to collect enough valid questionnaires, expand the sample size, and issue 480 questionnaires. (Wu Minglong (2010); Westland, c.J. (2010); Jak, S, Jorgensen, T.D, Verdam, M.G, Oort, F.J, (2021). In order to ensure the authenticity and reliability of the data, the sample selected the spectator over the age of 18 to fill in the questionnaire for in-depth understanding of the spectator Evaluation characteristics, Brand identity, Brand cognition, Brand Positioning of the specific measurement data. The author used SPSS and AMOS software to organize and analyze questionnaire data.

5. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELLING

Combined with the hypotheses of the previous research, structural equation modelling was constructed and the correlation lines between the independent variables were drawn, and substituting the data into AMOS 26 yielded the following results.

Figure 2: Operating results of structural equation model diagram (standardized)

Finally, a model of the influence of evaluating characteristics, Brand cognition, Brand identity on the brand positioning China was constructed (Chi-square=3625.006, DF=2635, Chi/DF=1.234, GFI=0.831, RMSEA=0.015, NFI=0.825, and NNFI=0.943). Therefore, this study is helpful to understand the overall status quo, influencing factors and mode promotion

and application of Jishou sport city brand, and to lay a certain theoretical foundation for the research related to the city brand of sport events.

Table 1: Hypotheses Testing Result of the Structural Model

Path			Non-standard load factor	S.E.	C.R.	P	Standardized load coefficient	Hypothesis
BP	<---	EC	0.215	0.054	3.658	***	0.194	H3
BP	<---	BC	0.238	0.033	5.275	***	0.205	H5
BP	<---	BI	0.215	0.047	3.759	***	0.243	H4
BI	<---	EC	0.253	0.069	3.435	***	0.224	H1
BC	<---	EC	0.133	0.048	2.786	0.004	0.214	H2

When $P < 0.05$ then the path is significant, and when the path is significant, the coefficient is positive then the independent variable has a significant positive effect on the dependent variable. From the above table, it can be seen that the independent variables Brand identity, Brand cognition, Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive effect on the dependent variable Brand Positioning.

6. MEDIATED EFFECTS TEST

The Bootstrap method can directly test the existence of mediating effects. The hypothesis for direct testing is $H_0: ab=0$. If the confidence interval obtained from the test results contains 0, that there is no mediating effect. Based on the results of path analysis, the hypothesis test is valid. In order to explore whether there is a mediating effect in these significant paths, we ran the Bootstrap method on AMOS 26.0, confidence interval standard of 95%, and bias correction method for testing.

Table 2: Mediation Effect

Regression path	Effect type	Effect	95% Lower	95% Upper	P
evaluating characteristics => Brand identity => brand positioning	Direct effect	0.253	0.105	0.432	0.001
	Indirect effect	0.054	0.013	0.115	0.001
	Total effect	0.321	0.176	0.503	0.000
Evaluation characteristics=>Brand cognition=>brand positioning	Direct effect	0.137	0.025	0.264	0.007
	Indirect effect	0.055	0.028	0.117	0.000
	Total effect	0.208	0.102	0.333	0.002

The mediation path evaluating characteristics => Brand identity => brand positioning holds true because its confidence interval does not contain the number 0. This shows that Brand identity mediates between evaluating characteristics and brand positioning. And the direct effect of the path is significant, the indirect effect is significant and the total effect is significant, which means that Trust plays a partial mediating role. The mediation path evaluation characteristics => Brand cognition => brand positioning holds true because its confidence interval does not contain the number 0. The mediation path of evaluation characteristics => Brand cognition => brand positioning is valid. And the direct effect of the path is significant, the indirect effect is significant, and the total effect is significant, indicating that Trust plays a partial mediating role.

7. CONCLUSION

This article takes Jishou residents as the survey object, uses qualitative and quantitative research methods, brand identity, brand cognition, evaluation characteristics on the brand positioning.

7.1 Qualitative analysis - interview results

Qualitative analysis results show that brand identity on the brand positioning and together provide important support for the construction of the Jishou sport City brand. Evaluation characteristics will help shape the image of the Jishou sport City brand and enhance the sense of identity and belonging of citizens and the outside world towards Jishou.

7.2 Quantitative analysis--model results

Brand identity has a significant positive impact on the difference of brand positioning, the accuracy of brand positioning and the brand positioning competitiveness. Brand cognition has a significant difference in brand positioning, accuracy of brand positioning and competitiveness of brand positioning Positive influence. Evaluation characteristics has a significant positive impact on the difference of brand positioning, the accuracy of brand positioning and the brand positioning competitiveness.

7.3 Qualitative analysis - expert interview panel

Through interviews with experts, we gained an in-depth understanding of the impact of sport events, integrated city values on the Jishou sport City brand. First of all, experts agree that the hosting of sport events is crucial to the brand building of Jishou sport City. They emphasized the necessity of multiple communication channels and believed that through evaluation characteristics, the characteristics and advantages of Jishou sport City can be more widely disseminated to various groups, thereby enhancing brand awareness and influence.

8. DISCUSSION

8.1 Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand identity

The findings indicate that Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand identity, Tian (2018) and Pan (2019), in the process of brand building of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival, audience evaluation characteristics are an important activity, and their evaluation is directly related to the public's brand recognition of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival.

8.2 Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand cognition

The results show that the evaluation characteristics of the audience have an important impact on the brand perception of the Jishou Drum Cultural Festival. As one of the core activities of Jishou City, the evaluation characteristics of the audience are directly related to the brand recognition and promotion of the Jishou Drum Cultural Festival, Wang (2020).

8.3 Evaluation characteristics have a significant positive impact on brand positioning

The results show that audience evaluation characteristics have a significant impact on brand

positioning. The audience evaluation characteristics are one of the important means of promotion and dissemination of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival. Its evaluation is directly related to the degree of trust in the Jishou Drum Cultural Festival.

8.4 Brand identity has a significant positive impact on brand positioning

The results of the study show that brand identity has a significant positive impact on brand positioning. As one of the core components of Chengdu Sports City, brand identity is directly related to the audience's brand positioning of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival.

8.5 Brand cognition has a significant positive impact on brand positioning

The results show that brand awareness has an important impact on the brand positioning of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival. As one of the key means of promotion and communication, the audience's brand awareness directly affects the brand positioning of the Jishou Drum Cultural Festival.

8.6 Brand identity plays a mediating role in the influence of evaluating characteristics on brand positioning

The results show that brand identity plays a mediating role in the influence of feature evaluation on brand positioning. Brand identity is one of the important means of brand positioning of Jishou Drum Cultural Festival, which affects the perception and attitude of stakeholders towards the brand.

8.7 Brand cognition plays a mediating role in the influence of evaluation characteristics on brand positioning

The results show that Brand cognition plays a mediating role in the influence of evaluation features on brand positioning. Dong (2023), Brand cognition is an important part of the brand building process of sports cities, which is directly related to the audience's positioning and attitude towards the brand.

9. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Through empirical analysis, we can know that brand reputation will have an impact on the difference, accuracy and competitiveness of brand positioning. Miao encouragement is a national Miao drum competition, with the nature of social welfare, so not only to make the audience satisfied with the products related to the event, but also to make some achievements in social welfare. Then, it is necessary to do well to make the perceived effect of the Miao encouragement competition brand match with the expectations of the audience, and enhance the social brand recognition of the audience. The experience can also affect whether customers continue to spend and inform others about positive reviews of the brand. Previously, Miao inspirational invited Ato to participate in the opening part of the event, but only hastily walked through the field, the reaction of the players on the field is also very indifferent, the audience was disappointed, the event extended to the whole brand of the event, Miao inspirational suffered controversy in the public opinion field. It was a very good opportunity to enhance the brand reputation and ultimately had the opposite effect. Nowadays, there is still a lot of room

for improvement, and it is not difficult to do. Miao encouraging official can through public welfare activities close the distance with the audience, improve the quality of the hardware and software game such as improve the level of the referee, upgrade broadcast technology, guide consumers to participate in the midfield link game for word of mouth marketing, should in each link, let a person from the heart was moved, resonate, so as to improve the audience brand identity, promote interpersonal communication, finally achieve want to brand positioning strategy effect.

References

- 1) Dong Xinhui.(2023).Research on the relationship between sport brand and spokesperson consistency, brand recognition and purchase intention , Shanghai Institute of Sport.
- 2) Jak, S, Jorgensen, T. D., Verdam, M. G, Oort, F. J, & Elffers, L. (2021). Analytical power calculations for structural equation modeling: A tutorial and Shiny app. Behavior Research Methods, 53, 1385--1406. 10.3758/s13428-020-01479-0.
- 3) Mao Junhan.(2023)The impact of virtual spokespersons in advertising on brand recognition: the moderating effect of product type, Shanghai International Studies University.
- 4) Pan Mingxu.(2019).Research on the service quality of the CBA League Shanghai Division based on the perception of the audience.Shanghai Sport University.
- 5) Su Wen.(2019). Research on Qujiang Cultural Tourism Brand Positioning. Northwest University.
- 6) Tian Yuan.(2018).Research on the organization and management of Jishou International Drum Culture Festival. Jishou University.
- 7) Wang Yidan.(2019). Research on Brand Building of Kung Fu All-Around Skills Events. Beijing: Beijing Sport University.
- 8) Wu Minglong.(2010). Operation and Application of the Structural Equation Model——AMOS (Version 2). Chongqing: Chongqing University Press.
- 9) Wen Lu.(2022). Research on Chengdu City Brand Positioning and Symbol Construction, Southwest University of Political Science and Law.
- 10) Westland,c.J.(2010),”Lower bounds on samplesize in structural equation modelling”,ElectronicCommerce Research and Applications, Vol. 9 No. 6,pp.476-487.
- 11) Xie Weitong, Hou Guohong.(2022). Brand recognition, consumer perception and purchase intention,Business Economics Research, (3): 83- 86.
- 12) Zhao Xiangzhong, Zhang Meng.(2019). Research on content marketing and brand loyalty based on brand awareness. Business Research, (01): 10-17.
- 13) Zhang Xiran.(2020). Research on the brand positioning of my country's gold label marathon events. Beijing: Capital Institute of Physical Education, 2020.
- 14) Zhou Xiaodan.(2023).Research on the Consumption Identity of National Sports Brands of Female College Students in Jinan.Shandong Normal University.